

CONCEPTUALISING VIRTUAL WORLDS

A NARRATIVE-DRIVEN
ARCHITECTURE

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Conceptualising Virtual Worlds: A Narrative-Driven Architecture

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Abstract

What are virtual worlds? For the purposes of this article, we assume that it is currently unknown what virtual worlds will look like. The definition of the metaverse, virtual world, or whatever we should call it – and what it will come to be – will likely depend on whose narrative or narratives are being pushed most forcefully,³ with some narratives already having failed the test of time. Nonetheless, one thing is certain: virtual worlds, supported by increasingly powerful AI systems, bear the potential to pervade human lives at a level hitherto unknown. It is therefore crucial that regulators not simply approach virtual worlds as another market or industry to be regulated. They should take an active part in the shaping of virtual worlds and not leave this process predominantly in the hands of private entities, especially given the difficulty of implementing structural regulation once the industry has matured.

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² Recipient of a DOC Fellowship of the Austrian Academy of Science at the Competition Law and Digitalization Group of the WU Vienna. Fabian is Of Counsel at AKELA RechtsanwältInnen GmbH. The author has no conflict of interest to disclose.

³ Matthew Ball, 'On Spatial Computing, Metaverse, the Terms Left Behind and Ideas Renewed' (matthewball.co, 06.02.2024) <https://www.matthewball.co/all/metaversespatialandmore>; Gaetano Dimita et. al., 'IP and Metaverse(s) – an externally commissioned research report' (Intellectual Property Office, 07.03.2024) 8-10.

I. Virtual worlds: old wine in new bottles?

Virtual worlds⁴ are growing out of existing ecosystems in video games, app stores and hardware. In this context, an ecosystem is a governance structure involving multiple actors, such as hardware providers, platform operators, and content developers, which together formulate a value proposition, generally through complementary products and services.⁵ Therefore, currently, the main players in virtual world development have already been around for some time, and some of them wield considerable economic and ecosystem power.⁶ Ecosystem power refers to the ability of dominant companies to lock in users, collect data, and influence the behaviour of other companies in the system.⁷ Consequently, virtual worlds are bound to become a narrative-driven architecture, in the sense that what the platforms will ultimately look like depends heavily on whose narrative will persevere. This is, however, not to say that there are no new players and business models in virtual world development. In this Section I, we highlight the connections between virtual world development and existing ecosystems, in particular video games. Building on Section I, Sections II and III highlight the specificities of virtual worlds and emerging players and business models. Section IV touches on the role of interoperability and open standards in the context of the strategic incentives of incumbent companies. Lastly, we outline in Section V that current regulatory approaches, such as the Digital Markets Act (DMA), fall short of addressing emerging virtual worlds, instead treating the symptoms rather than the root causes of entrenched economic power.

In June 2023, the European Commission (EC) provided a definition of virtual worlds focusing on three elements (1) *platform* ('persistent, immersive environments'), (2) *means of access* ('based on technologies including 3D and extended reality (XR)'), and (3) *purpose* ('blend physical and digital worlds [...] for a variety of purposes such as [...] entertainment').⁸ We need to look no further than the General Secretariat of the Council's publication on the metaverse to see a similar definition that focuses on (1) *platform* ('an immersive and constant virtual 3D world'), (2) *purpose* ('where people interact through an avatar to enjoy entertainment'), and (3) *means of access*

⁴ The term 'virtual worlds' appears to us as the latest iteration of 'metaverse', since the latter lost some of its appeal after Facebook's rebranding to Meta. We do not have a preference on the choice of term and note that many still opt for 'metaverse'.

⁵ Michael G. Jacobides, Carmel Cennamo and Annabelle Gawer, 'Distinguishing between Platforms and Ecosystems: Complementarities, Value Creation, and Coordination Mechanisms' (jacobides.com, 2020) <https://www.jacobides.com/ongoing-projects> 13-19.

⁶ For instance, in terms of cloud (gaming) infrastructure, see Damien Geradin and Stijn Huijts 'Dark clouds gather - The development of cloud gaming, and competition agencies' efforts to enable it on mobile app stores' (2023) 6(1) Interactive Entertainment Law Review 3.

⁷ Michael G. Jacobides and Ioannis Lianos, 'Ecosystems and Competition Law in Theory and Practice' (2021) 30(5) Industrial and Corporate Change 1199.

⁸ EC, 'Communication from the Commission - An EU initiative on Web 4.0 and virtual worlds' (11.07.2023) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52023DC0442> 1.

(‘accessible through a virtual reality (VR) headset’),⁹ which echoes the sentiments of President von der Leyen on the future of the metaverse.¹⁰

Many of these EU publications focus on the novel aspects of virtual worlds. For example, the EC emphasized the emergence of virtual worlds with Web 4.0, which does not even exist yet. However, a focus on novelty risks obfuscating the clear links between the video game industry and virtual worlds,¹¹ as well as the efforts of established digital ecosystem providers to push for specific visions of virtual worlds in a way that leverages their existing ecosystems,¹² as discussed further in Section I a), as well as Section I b) and II respectively.

First of all, the same three elements have been the ubiquitous standard for evaluating any type of video game and gaming hardware: (1) *platform* – a video game and/or game engine;¹³ (2) *means of access* – personal computer, (portable) console, or mobile phone; and (3) *purpose* – genres, e.g., shooter, multiplayer online battle arena (MOBA), sports simulation, sandbox or more specifically subgenres, e.g., tactical and battle royale shooter.¹⁴ Virtual worlds will expand the number of concurrent users or players in a virtual location, subject to overcoming spatial partitioning,¹⁵ and will provide (in fact, are already providing) use cases other than and including video games.¹⁶

The evolution of virtual worlds from the gaming sector was part of the *Epic v. Apple* saga in the United States. The case concerned Apple’s app store distribution policies – contractual and technical – which prevented developers from opening their own app stores and steering users to cheaper purchasing options for game-related transactions like skin purchases. The dispute revealed that the CEO of Epic Games, Tim Sweeney, had a clear vision to develop Fortnite into a metaverse. The court explained that [a] metaverse is a virtual world in which a user can

⁹ General Secretariat of the Council (Council of the European Union), ‘Metaverse Virtual world, real challenges’ (European Council, 09.03.2022) <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/93dbc29a-4ad0-11ee-aeff-01aa75ed71a1/1,2>.

¹⁰ EC, ‘People, technologies & infrastructure – Europe’s plan to thrive in the metaverse’ (14.09.2022) https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/es/STATEMENT_22_5525.

¹¹ Brian E. Mennecke et. al., ‘Second Life and Other Virtual Worlds: A Roadmap for Research’ (2008) 22 Communications of the Association for Information Systems 371.

¹² John Naughton, ‘The metaverse is dystopian – but to big tech it’s a business opportunity’ (Guardian, 29.01.2022) <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2022/jan/29/the-metaverse-is-dystopian-but-to-big-tech-its-a-business-opportunity>.

¹³ One could even start a level above the game engine, by considering the operating system. See, for example, *Microsoft/Activision Blizzard* (Case M.10646) Commission Decision of 15 June 2023.

¹⁴ Fabian Ziermann, ‘Assessing the World’s Largest Gaming Acquisition under EU Competition Law’ (2023a) 14(4) JECLAP 203.

¹⁵ Most games are limited to 100-120 player per region, see: Kendra M. L. Cooper and Walt Scacchi (eds), *Computer Games and Software Engineering* (1st edn, CRC Press, 2020) 155-160.

¹⁶ Pearl Academy, ‘Unreal Engine: Applications Beyond Gaming’ (Pearl Academy, 29.03.2024) <https://blog.pearlacademy.com/unreal-engine-applications-beyond-gaming/>.

experience many different things—consume content, transact, interact with friends and family, as well as play. According to Mr. Sweeney, game play need not be a part of a user’s metaverse experience, which is more to mimic the reality of life than to present game play.¹⁷ The district court emphasised the distinction between developer-created experiences vs user-created experiences on Fortnite¹⁸, and Tim Sweeney’s vision of Fortnite shifting the emphasis from the former to the latter based on his ‘sincerely held’ beliefs about the future of the metaverse.

While the court ultimately fell short of recognizing Fortnite as a metaverse platform, this was arguably only because ‘Fortnite itself is both externally and internally considered a video game [and] there is no evidence or opinion in the record that a video game like Fortnite is considered by its parts (i.e., the modes within the game) instead of in its totality.’¹⁹ To rephrase, if Epic were to change its marketing approach, and users embraced this transformation, a legally recognised metaverse or virtual world could already be in existence.

The court’s recognition of narrative-driven virtual worlds is important to note against the background that it is difficult to speak of the failure of virtual worlds, the metaverse, or similar constructs,²⁰ so long as there is not a total failure and discontinuation of video games. What has failed in recent months is the narrative that companies like Meta sought to establish in an attempt to become the prevailing metaverse company, whereas platforms like Roblox continue to thrive through a community-centric approach.²¹ That virtual worlds as a whole will fail is unlikely, given the number of (game) platforms that are working on transcending their standing as a video game.

a) Platform

The video game origins shape the current competitive landscape of virtual worlds. It is possible that the market-leading *platform* of the future already exists as a precursor, with Fortnite, Minecraft, and Roblox being the most promising examples,²² or that it is yet to be created. The *platform* element is, at least for now, primarily driven by gaming companies, their platforms and

¹⁷ Epic Games, Inc. v. Apple Inc. 559 F. Supp. 3d 898 (N.D. Cal. 2021) 974, also at 935.

¹⁸ The court also noted the user created experiences in Roblox. See *ibid* at 935.

¹⁹ *ibid* at 974–975.

²⁰ Michael G. Jacobides et. al., ‘Building synthetic worlds: lessons from the excessive infatuation and oversold disillusionment with the metaverse’ (2024) 31(1) *Industry and Innovation* 105.

²¹ See *ibid* 121. We note however the backlash that Roblox is currently facing in terms of the protection of children’s safety on the platform. See, for example, Libby Brooks and Jedidajah Otteh, ‘Risks to children playing Roblox “deeply disturbing”, say researchers’ (Guardian, 14.04.2025) <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2025/apr/14/risks-children-roblox-deeply-disturbing-researchers>.

²² Team Exponential, ‘Can Fortnite, Minecraft, and Roblox Create an Interoperable Metaverse?’ (Medium, 29.10.2024) https://medium.com/@exponential_64626/can-fortnite-minecraft-and-roblox-create-an-interoperable-metaverse-b4b730b6d706.

other platform capabilities, such as Epic Games' Fortnite and the Unreal Engine, Microsoft's Minecraft, and platforms like Roblox or Decentraland, which do not offer XR immersion. This is perhaps best illustrated by Fortnite's expansion from the battle royale shooter subgenre to virtual worlds, leveraging the network effects of its player base and eSports and gaming ecosystem.²³ Each of these companies has a unique selling point, such as Roblox's focus on facilitating cross-platform creation, which has enabled it to amass 350 million monthly active users, while Fortnite hosts an ecosystem of virtual worlds with transportable accessories: in Ball's words, a cross-entitlement platform.²⁴ Pokémon Go and virtual eSports arenas (eva.gg) are examples of partial and full immersion respectively.

If we unpack this picture, one thing becomes clear: there are not many players that can develop large-scale virtual world platforms. The most relevant platforms today are Roblox, Fortnite (40% owned by Tencent), and Minecraft (owned by Microsoft). Decentraland, The Sandbox, and Second Life are also well-known, but user numbers on these platforms are incomparable to the clout of the former three companies.

While platforms like Roblox have seen significant user numbers in recent years²⁵, and despite annual revenues of \$2.8 billion in 2023 in the case of Roblox,²⁶ the company also reported a net loss of \$1.158 billion in 2023 - its net losses have grown exponentially since 2018 due to the need for significant investment,²⁷ with R&D and infrastructure spending at more than \$2.1 billion annually.²⁸ Similarly, in 2023, Epic Games faced approximately \$4.9 billion in costs of sales,²⁹ compared to \$5.6 billion in gross revenue.³⁰ In other words, building virtual worlds requires high investment costs (barriers to entry) that only a few companies, such as an independent

²³ Andrew Webster, 'Fortnite is winning the metaverse' (The Verge, 08.02.2024) <https://www.theverge.com/24065901/fortnite-metaverse-disney-epic-partnership>; Rajesh Mani Kumar G, 'The Future of Virtual Worlds: Comparing Metaverse, Second Life, Fortnite, and World of Warcraft' (Medium, 04.03.2024) <https://medium.com/@rajeshmanikumarg/the-future-of-virtual-worlds-comparing-metaverse-second-life-fortnite-and-world-of-warcraft-b940feed3958>.

²⁴ Ben Thompson (2024a) 'An Interview with Matthew Ball About the Vision Pro and the State of Gaming' (Stratechery, 22.02.2024) <https://stratechery.com/2024/an-interview-with-matthew-ball-about-the-vision-pro-and-the-state-of-gaming/>.

²⁵ Roblox was launched in 2006.

²⁶ J. Clement, 'Roblox Corporation global revenue 2018-2023' (Statista, 28.02.2024) <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1190638/quarterly-revenue-roblox-corporation/>.

²⁷ J. Clement, 'Roblox Corporation global net loss 2018-2023' (Statista, 28.02.2024) <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1190266/annual-consolidated-net-loss-roblox-corporation/>.

²⁸ J. Clement, 'Roblox Corporation global OPEX 2020-2023' (Statista, 29.02.2024) <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1377017/annual-opex-roblox-corporation/>.

²⁹ J. Clement, 'Epic Games annual cost of sales 2018-2026' (Statista, 08.12.2023) <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1234212/epic-games-annual-cost-of-sales/>.

³⁰ J. Clement, 'Epic Games annual gross revenue 2018-2026' (Statista, 08.12.2023) <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1234106/epic-games-annual-revenue/>.

Activision Blizzard, could afford.³¹ Moreover, monthly active users of Roblox, Fortnite and Minecraft are between 350 and 166 million respectively,³² compared to several hundred thousand for The Sandbox, Decentraland and Second Life combined. Monthly active users in smaller platforms are difficult to quantify due to the lack of official reports, but their numbers appear to pale in comparison to Roblox, Fortnite and Minecraft.

Massively Multiplayer Online Role-Playing Games (MMORPGs) are also seen as a precursor to virtual worlds and require similar capabilities. The most important are World of Warcraft (now owned by Microsoft), The Elder Scrolls Online (owned by Microsoft), Eve Online, and Guild Wars 2. Riot Games is reportedly working on an MMORPG,³³ but since it is 100% owned by Tencent, and due to Tencent's 40% stake in Epic Games (Fortnite), it is unlikely that these games will compete and thereby cannibalise each other. Idem for the battle royale shooter genre. The most relevant players in this genre are Fortnite (40% owned by Tencent), Call of Duty (now owned by Microsoft), Apex Legends (Developer Respawn Entertainment owned by Electronic Arts), PlayerUnknown's Battlegrounds (PUBG) (13.73% owned by Tencent), and Garena Free Fire (18.7% owned by Tencent).³⁴ In addition to these holdings, Tencent continues to increase its direct and indirect ownership of Ubisoft,³⁵ and other companies.³⁶ An overall picture of ownership structure of game studios as of February 2022 (including Microsoft's acquisition of Activision Blizzard, which has since taken place) shows that post-acquisition Microsoft controls 32 game studios, followed by Sony and Electronic Arts which each own 21 studios, and Tencent owning 14 studios.³⁷ Lax merger control in the eSports and gaming space has facilitated this picture of concentration and

³¹ Vice versa, this means that access to funding constitutes a barrier to entry for the virtual world layer, discussed below.

³² See respectively, Thompson (2024a); Naveen Kumar, 'Fortnite Statistics 2025: Revenue & Active Users Data' (Demandsage, 01.01.2025) <https://www.demandsage.com/fortnite-statistics/>; Naveen Kumar, 'How Many People Play Minecraft 2025 (Active Players)' (Demandsage, 01.01.2025) <https://www.demandsage.com/minecraft-statistics/>.

³³ Abhishek Mallick, 'Riot Games League of Legends MMORPG: Release window, what to expect, and more' (sportskeeda, 11.07.2023).

³⁴ Steven Messner, 'Every game company that Tencent has invested in' (PCGamer, 09.08.2020) <https://www.pcgamer.com/every-game-company-that-tencent-has-invested-in/>; Hwang Soon-min and Yoon Yeon-ae, 'China, Saudi Arabia eye Korean game companies' (Pulse, 06.12.2023) <https://pulse.mk.co.kr/news/english/10891956>; Garena Free Fire: Anshuman Daga, Kane Wu and Scott Murdoch, 'Tencent raises \$3 bln by trimming stake in Shopee-owner Sea' (Reuters, 05.01.2022) <https://www.reuters.com/technology/tencent-reduce-voting-stake-singapore-tech-group-sea-2022-01-04/>.

³⁵ Dean Takahashi, 'Ubisoft beefs up ties to Tencent through sale of Guillemot Brothers Ltd. stake' (GamesBeat, 06.09.2022) <https://venturebeat.com/games/ubisoft-beefs-up-ties-to-tencent-through-sale-of-guillemot-brothers-ltd-stake/>.

³⁶ Steven Messner, 'Every game company that Tencent has invested in' (PCGamer, 09.08.2020).

³⁷ Florian Zandt, 'The Gaming Giants Building A Studio Empire' (Statista, 02.02.2022) <https://www.statista.com/chart/26756/number-of-first-party-studios-owned-by-selected-public-video-game-companies/>.

cross-ownership, with market concentration continuing to increase.³⁸ As we wrote elsewhere, the EC's clearance of the *Microsoft/Activision Blizzard* merger has implications not just for video games but also virtual worlds.³⁹

b) Means of access

The *means of access* to virtual worlds does not need to be VR technology: this is an idea that is being driven primarily by the undertakings that stand to gain the most from its adoption.⁴⁰ Similar to video games, virtual worlds can be accessed without VR technology, via PCs, consoles, and mobile devices. This certainly results in a different level of immersion, affecting what kind of purposes can be facilitated, however, interpreting the EC's definition to only capture VR or comparable means of access risks constraining virtual worlds to the business models some companies want to implement and prematurely excludes platforms that embody similar features, yet do so through different means of access. After all, as outlined above, if Epic Games would have pursued a different marketing strategy for Fortnite, a legally recognised 'virtual world' would be in existence without VR access. As discussed further in Section 2, Meta and Apple will likely try to ensure that virtual worlds necessitate some form of VR/AR⁴¹/XR *means of access*. They are popularising the business model that Apple has succeeded with for smartphones, i.e. a device-centric bottleneck that allows Apple and Meta to control everything that happens in this new virtual environment.⁴² Instead of the iPhone and the App Store, the means of access is a Meta Quest coupled with Meta Quest Store and Apple Vision Pro coupled with its dedicated app store. Given the challenges of regulating Apple's and Google's smartphone and app dominance, the EC must consider whether it is desirable to allow this business model to become entrenched for the next hardware technology.

c) Purpose

Purpose, use cases, or content is largely determined by what original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) and platform orchestrators deem as most useful to attract users and/or provide greater control. It is best understood on a spectrum. This ranges from doctors using AR for training

³⁸ See, for example, Anirban Sen and Sam Nussey, 'Exclusive: Sony is in talks to buy media powerhouse behind "Elden Ring" (Reuters, 19.11.2024) <https://www.reuters.com/markets/deals/sony-talks-buy-media-powerhouse-behind-elden-ring-sources-say-2024-11-19/>.

³⁹ Ayşe Gizem Yaşar, Amy Thomas, Kenny Barr, Magali Eben, 'Gaming without Frontiers: Copyright and Competition in the Changing Video Game Sector' CREATE Working Paper 2023/10, 32-33.

⁴⁰ Mike Isaac, 'Meta Unveils New Smart Glasses and Headsets in Pursuit of the Metaverse' (The New York Times, 25.09.2024) <https://www.nytimes.com/2024/09/25/technology/meta-products-artificial-intelligence.html>.

⁴¹ AR stands for augmented reality.

⁴² See, to that effect, Carliss Y. Baldwin, 'Bottlenecks, Modules and Dynamic Architectural Capabilities' (SSRN, 09.06.2015) https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2512209.

purposes, to the already alarming rate of mental health issues exacerbated by living in an immersive virtual society.⁴³ *Purpose* becomes economically and competitively problematic when the OEM or platform orchestrator also controls it. For instance, it is advantageous for Apple to have exclusive rights to Major League Soccer (MLS), allowing it to make investments that are not possible in the National Football League (NFL) due to fragmented rights.⁴⁴ This exclusivity makes it more lucrative for Apple to develop and offer immersive experiences, such as featuring 8K 3D video with a 180-degree field of view and Spatial Audio, available exclusively on Apple Vision Pro, as it is the sole beneficiary of its investment. In contrast, multiple networks and streaming platforms hold NFL media rights, complicating the development and implementation of a standardised VR experience. But linking MLS to the Vision Pro may initially be attractive until Apple can control all uses of MLS content. This is as much a competition issue as it is an intellectual property issue, since the full control is made possible and implemented through IP rights.⁴⁵

II. Assessing virtual world layers

It has become commonplace to describe virtual worlds within a layered structure. Many examples exist⁴⁶ and they essentially boil down to five layers, which we map on the three definitional elements discussed in Section 1. Different layers come with distinct challenges in development and deployment.

⁴³ Paquin et al, 'Time to Think "Meta": A Critical Viewpoint on the Risks and Benefits of Virtual Worlds for Mental Health' JMIR Serious Games (07.02.2023) <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36661284/>.

⁴⁴ Thompson (2024a).

⁴⁵ For a similar analysis in the case of the internet, see Taylor B Bartholomew, 'The Death of Fair Use in Cyberspace: YouTube and the Problem With Content ID' (2015) 13 Duke Law & Technology Review 66.

⁴⁶ Jon Radoff, 'The Metaverse Value-Chain' (Medium, 07.04.2021) <https://medium.com/building-the-metaverse/the-metaverse-value-chain-afcf9e09e3a7>.

	Infrastructure	Hardware and software infrastructure that virtual worlds are built on, such as telecommunication infrastructure, chips and processors, and cloud. ⁴⁷
Access	Hardware	'physical technologies and devices for private users, enterprise users and developers of [virtual worlds]. Desktop computers, AR/VR headsets, mobile devices, haptic wearables, 3D cameras fall into this category.' ⁴⁸
Platform	Engine	Software dedicated to the creation of virtual worlds and experiences, such as Unity and Amazon Sumerian.
	Virtual world	This is the core layer, i.e. the 'meta, persistent, immersive, interactive, and interconnected' environment. ⁴⁹ App stores are not in themselves virtual worlds, but they might be integrated into specific virtual worlds for distribution of experiences, or they might be used to distribute virtual worlds in future.
Purpose	Experience	This layer includes virtual experiences for end users, which might range from video games, live concerts and sports events to simulation of real-life or complex virtual experiences that do not have a real-life component, like time travel.

Table 1: Virtual worlds value chain

At the infrastructure and hardware layers, *access to finance* is a major challenge for potential entrants. While funding is a necessary component for any venture, it is especially difficult to raise for hardware projects, which is likely to tilt the balance in favour of established players sitting on cash reserves such as Meta. Currently, Nvidia is spearheading chip development for virtual reality applications, building on its expertise in games. While Intel signalled its own entry

⁴⁷ Payment systems are sometimes described as a sixth layer, due to the necessity to integrate them into digital environments where monetary transactions take place. They could be considered within the infrastructure layer.

⁴⁸ Yaşar et al (2023) 30.

⁴⁹ ibid 27.

into the 'metaverse' in 2021,⁵⁰ it is unclear whether the project is still live. Apple has succeeded in developing its own silicon for Mac, and its new headset Vision Pro is also powered by its new R1 chip. Other than these established players, there are no new players in sight, with the possible exception of a chip venture by Sam Altman.⁵¹ In terms of hardware, entry by new companies remains rare, with established players providing the most popular hardware. For example, in VR/spatial computing headsets (which we collectively refer to as VR headsets), the main players are Meta (Quest), PlayStation (Pulse) and HTC (Vive). ByteDance had entered the VR space with Pico, but the future of ByteDance's VR operations is currently uncertain.⁵² The latest entrant is, as is well known, Apple.

Capabilities and frontiers of the virtual world layer will be defined by computing power and hardware capabilities. Hardware capabilities at the point of end user access is not a barrier to growth as such on this particular layer. Video games have thrived on a variety of hardware, in particular consoles, PCs and mobile devices, and virtual worlds will also be accessed through different types of hardware. That said, *access to computing power (infrastructure)* is both an enabler and a barrier to entry at the virtual world layer.⁵³ Developers of virtual worlds need to maintain and consistently update the backbone, be it proprietary or licensed/purchased on-demand from third parties. For example, Roblox runs 'a custom-built and hybrid private cloud infrastructure that runs primarily on premises.'⁵⁴

At the engine, virtual world and experience layers, *IP rights* are both an enabler and a barrier to entry.⁵⁵ Each virtual world and each experience will likely integrate hundreds or thousands of IP-protected elements. Asset stores like Unity and Unreal have allowed developers to overcome IP rights conflicts to some extent in the video game sector, and a similar approach might be expected in virtual worlds. But there is still a risk that existing market power could be translated

⁵⁰ Raja Koduri, 'Powering the Metaverse: Intel is working on the plumbing for a persistent and immersive internet.' (14.12.2021) <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/newsroom/opinion/powering-metaverse.html>; Dean Takahashi, 'Nvidia and Intel team up on chips for metaverse workstations' (VentureBeat, 15.02.2023) <https://venturebeat.com/games/nvidia-and-intel-team-up-on-chips-for-metaverse-workstations/>.

⁵¹ Beatrice Nolan, 'Sam Altman wants Washington's backing for his \$7 trillion AI chip venture' (Business Insider, 16.02.2024) <https://www.businessinsider.com/sam-altman-wants-government-backing-7-trillion-ai-chip-venture-2024-2>.

⁵² Qianer Liu, Wenjie Ding in Beijing, Tim Bradshaw 'ByteDance's virtual reality division announces restructuring and staff cuts' (Financial Times, 07.11.2023) <https://www.ft.com/content/2b812a27-4cd1-4b85-862a-5da05cd1650a>.

⁵³ Compare concerning AI: Jai Vipra and Sarah Myers West, 'Computational Power and AI' (AI Now Institute, 27.09.2023) <https://ainowinstitute.org/publication/policy/compute-and-ai#h-what-is-compute-and-why-does-it-matter>.

⁵⁴ Daniel Sturman, 'How We're Making Roblox's Infrastructure More Efficient and Resilient' (Roblox Blog, 07.12.23) <https://blog.roblox.com/2023/12/making-robloxs-infrastructure-efficient-resilient/>.

⁵⁵ Dimita et al (2024) 19-34, 38-48.

to these layers, enabling incumbents to become the de-facto standard-setters, e.g., large IPR licensees like Alphabet might hold an advantage over entrants.

If an undertaking is integrated across multiple layers, *vertical integration* will give rise to foreclosure concerns.⁵⁶ The competition between hardware OEMs is most analogous to the competition between Apple and Google in the smartphone market, assuming however, that each offers an app store, a device and an operating system. The only question in this context is whether the competition between hardware OEMs is seen as competition to become the dominant *means of access* to a third-party *platform*, or whether each has a closed ecosystem (in terms of *platform*) and seeks to retain users within that ecosystem without facilitating interoperability. In any event, both Apple and Meta, the two notable competitors in this landscape, have the necessary financial resources to enjoy a first-shaper advantage by translating their business model (Apple) or adopting another successful business model (Meta) to the virtual world market.⁵⁷ If Apple or Meta were to succeed in establishing a VR-driven virtual world, they would ultimately control the bottleneck (VR headsets) and thus could dictate what the other elements of the ecosystem look like.

This is also the case for *platform* providers like Fortnite or Roblox, in terms of what technology they want to grant access to or how they want to design their ecosystem, i.e., controlling the *platform* bottleneck. The biggest concern is that one undertaking (or a few) would control the dominant *platform* and the *means of access*, as this would create two layers or bottlenecks to control the ecosystem. For example, if Meta Quest and Fortnite prevail, we are likely to find ourselves in a world where exclusivity agreements such as those currently in place between Google and Apple regarding search browser defaults, could become the new standard for virtual worlds, albeit on a different subject matter. It is however unlikely that players not providing *access* or *platforms* could create anticompetitive bottlenecks, due to the limited or complementary importance of other layers.

III. What is new about virtual worlds?

While virtual worlds are currently developed on existing ecosystems, there are also new actors and business models across different layers of virtual worlds. The greatest flow of entry is likely

⁵⁶ If key players control multiple layers, this may give rise to foreclosure concerns, see Dwayne Bach and Fabian Ziermann, 'Conglomerate foreclosure in the metaverse' (D'Kart, 22.06.2022) <https://www.d-kart.de/blog/2022/06/22/conglomerate-foreclosure-in-the-metaverse/>.

⁵⁷ Comparable to first-mover advantage, however, with the distinction that moving first in itself does not provide the competitive advantage of shaping the emerging market so that competition is automatically reduced, e.g., by controlling or setting up a bottleneck in the new market early on and thus dictating other standards.

to take place at the experience layer. There is a probability that the experience layer will have a bottom-up effect on the development of higher layers, which is why the virtual world value chain has been described as a 'supply chain of content'.⁵⁸ In particular, *events with physical capacity* like concerts and sports games will likely flourish in virtual worlds. In a similar vein, virtual worlds can allow such experiences to happen with a close-up, e.g., as if the spectator is standing right in front of the singer at a concert. Both established and novel platforms are already providing such services. Concerts already happen on Fortnite and Roblox.⁵⁹ There are platforms dedicated to virtual events, like AmazeVR.⁶⁰ Apple pitched Vision Pro to consumers with 'an intimate rehearsal with Alicia Keys'.⁶¹

Complex virtual experiences that do not have a real-life component are also likely to flourish in virtual worlds. Once again, this is not a novelty: space and time travel experiences, science fiction experiences, for example, have existed for as long as video games have – stories have existed for even longer. NASA offered its free virtual reality program for Oculus Rift.⁶² Increased complexity might mean that, at least to a certain extent, such experiences will be provided in specialised environments for full immersion in a way reminiscent of game arcades. In a similar vein, *bespoke virtual environments* are emerging, offered by companies with or without proprietary technology. For example, Improbable uses its own technology to 'design, build, operate and service metaverse experiences'.⁶³

Generative AI-based creativity tools are expected to simplify the creation of virtual worlds and experiences. Such tools can go a long way in decreasing costs associated with the experience design process in terms of graphics, coding, and storytelling.⁶⁴ Generative AI use cases for virtual worlds/metaverse are already proliferating.⁶⁵ For example, OpenAI's new tool Sora creates video

⁵⁸ Thompson (2024a). See also Di Porto et al, 'Emerging Virtual Worlds: Implications for Policy and Regulation' CERRE Report, February 2024, especially 20-21 on 'mass content creation'.

⁵⁹ David Pierce, 'The concert of the future is already happening in the metaverse' (The Verge, 03.10. 2022) <https://www.theverge.com/2022/10/3/23384883/concerts-metaverse-travis-scott-charlie-puth-iheartland>.

⁶⁰ <https://www.amazevr.com>.

⁶¹ Apple Music, 'Experience Alicia Keys: Rehearsal Room on Apple Vision Pro' (02.02.2024) <https://youtu.be/d555q5vaYns?si=hWBlot5i8wRnKOfd>.

⁶² 'Free Virtual Reality Program: NASA SLS VR Experience' <https://www.nasa.gov/stem-content/free-virtual-reality-program-nasa-sls-vr-experience/>. This page does not provide any information on whether the program was migrated to Meta Quest after Oculus was discontinued.

⁶³ <https://www.improbable.io/ventures>.

⁶⁴ BCG, 'This Is How GenAI Could Accelerate the Metaverse' (16.08.2023) <https://www.bcg.com/publications/2023/how-gen-ai-could-accelerate-metaverse>.

⁶⁵ Jon Radoff, 'Generative AI x Automation for Virtual Worlds' (Metavert Meditations, 13.03.2023) <https://meditations.metavert.io/p/generative-ai-x-automation-for-virtual>; GPTPlus, 'AI-Powered Virtual Worlds' (Medium, 08.11.2023) <https://medium.com/@GPTPlus/ai-powered-virtual-worlds-ed2f581b7969>.

from text instructions⁶⁶ and it will likely be used for virtual world development.⁶⁷ Nvidia is developing generative AI for virtual world assets and other use cases in virtual worlds, both leveraging its own capabilities but also in partnership with other companies.⁶⁸ Generative AI companies catering specially to video games and virtual worlds include Promethean AI⁶⁹, Convai,⁷⁰ Inworld⁷¹ and Atlas.⁷²

The level and speed of entry at the experience level will likely depend on what the platforms permit. Engine and virtual world terms and conditions, including end-user licensing agreements (EULAs), might act as obstacles to the development of experiences. The most appropriate case study for this are complementary markets in eSports and gaming ecosystems, in particular streaming and content creation. While it has long been recognised that contemporary video games, due to free-to-play business models and microtransactions, instead of upfront purchases,⁷³ require increased life spans to monetise users, and that streaming and content creation provide such boosts,⁷⁴ publishers differ in their approaches. Most facilitate streaming and content creation to boost the experience surrounding their game.⁷⁵ There are exceptions: Nintendo requires the sharing of advertisement revenues from content creators, whilst prohibiting streams that display game content.⁷⁶ In other words, Nintendo, through the use of EULAs, constrains the development of experiences, representing a more closed ecosystem.

On a final note, the EC focused on 'virtual world markets' in its 2024 public consultation on virtual worlds and in other EU publications. Despite clear links to established ecosystems, virtual world systems have the potential to reach a point of pervasiveness hitherto unknown in digital ecosystems. While we commend the EC's plans to introduce a public interest project (European CitiVerse), the EU must contribute directly and indirectly to increase the number of public

⁶⁶ <https://openai.com/sora>.

⁶⁷ Ben Thompson (2024b) 'Sora, Groq, and Virtual Reality' (Stratechery, 20.02.2024) <https://stratechery.com/2024/sora-groq-and-virtual-reality/>.

⁶⁸ <https://developer.nvidia.com/blog/rapidly-generate-3d-assets-for-virtual-worlds-with-generative-ai/>.

⁶⁹ <https://www.prometheanai.com>.

⁷⁰ <https://inworld.ai>.

⁷¹ <https://inworld.ai>.

⁷² <https://atlas.design>.

⁷³ Alexander Bernevega and Alex Gekker, 'The Industry of Landlords: Exploring the Assetization of the Triple-A Game' (2021) 17(1) Games and Culture 47.

⁷⁴ Mark R Johnson and Jamie Woodcock, 'The impacts of live streaming and Twitch.tv on the video game industry' (2019) 41(5) Media, Culture & Society 670.

⁷⁵ Amy Thomas, 'Merit and monetisation: A study of video game user-generated content policies' (2023) 12(1) Internet Policy Review.

⁷⁶ Nan Li, 'Essays on Demand Spillovers in the Video-Game Industry' (The University of Rochester, 2019) <https://urresearch.rochester.edu/institutionalPublicationPublicView.action?institutionalItemId=34829>.

projects in virtual worlds, and not leave the development of virtual worlds predominantly in the hands of private entities.

IV. Interoperability and open standards

True interoperability, backed by open standards, does not appear likely to emerge anytime soon in virtual world development.⁷⁷ EC's emphasis on interoperability and open standards in various publications on virtual worlds and Web 4.0 is commendable, but we caution against an over-reliance on interoperability to ensure virtual world markets remain open. This is due to technical barriers, developer incentives, and user incentives.

At least at the experience level, a degree of seamless integration and movement across virtual worlds seems to be the desired outcome. Efforts to build spaces where open standards can be developed, such as the *Metaverse Standards Forum* or the *Metaverse Society* attest to this willingness. However, technical barriers remain. For example, full system interoperability may require rethinking single-client dominated virtual world ecosystems, with different players running different elements of virtual worlds across and within each layer of the virtual world value chain.⁷⁸

There are also signs that closed ecosystems are emerging, especially from Apple and Meta, as discussed above. When it comes to business users of such ecosystems, particularly developers of experiences, we may once again not find clear incentives for interoperability. First, interoperability means ceding control over proprietary technology, at least to some extent. Furthermore, proprietary systems and walled gardens have some clear benefits in the video game industry, as they fund independent games.⁷⁹ Indie game developers face relatively large upfront costs and commissions from proprietary platforms help overcome these cost barriers.⁸⁰

End users may not necessarily demand interoperability either, as users of digital services today are used to multi-homing or locked into specific ecosystems.⁸¹ Indeed, retail brands who have

⁷⁷ See to that effect Dimita et al. (2024) 11-12, 38-41.

⁷⁸ Anthony Steed, 'Three technical challenges of scaling from social virtual reality to metaverse(s): interoperability, awareness and accessibility' (2024) 5 *Front. Virtual Real.*

⁷⁹ Or Creators, e.g., Roblox's approach as discussed by Ball in Matthew Ball, *The Metaverse: And How It Will Revolutionize Everything* (2022, Norton & Company) 284.

⁸⁰ This point was raised at the CREATE roundtable of 17 February 2023 on 'Copyright, Competition and Business Models in App Stores and Gaming'. Event highlights are available at <https://www.create.ac.uk/blog/2023/03/14/copyright-competition-and-business-models-in-app-stores-and-gaming-event-highlights/>.

⁸¹ This point was originally raised at the CREATE workshop of 14 November 2023 titled 'Competition, copyright, and business models: what can academia and policy learn from the industry, and how can we help?' The workshop was held under Chatham House rules. Event highlights are available at

entered proto-metaverses like Nike or Gucci through Nikeland or Gucci Garden on Roblox or Timberland's experience in Fortnite have so far largely limited their operations to a selected number of platforms, or even a single platform.

V. Suitability of regulatory strategies

In our view, the single most important competition problem in virtual world development today is rising concentration and cross-ownership. In this context, video games and virtual worlds cannot be separated, as market power in existing video game ecosystems will translate into market power in virtual worlds as discussed in Section 1 above. Current regulatory strategy for both games and virtual worlds needs to be reconsidered, as it appears inadequate for both, with lax merger control and the acquisition of significant stakes in competing game publishers having contributed to the current concentration in the gaming industry and virtual worlds. Treating concentration issues in virtual worlds as swiftly as possible is all the more important considering the level of pervasiveness virtual worlds are likely to attain in our lives.

The EC Communication of 2023 on virtual worlds 'sets out the strategy and proposed actions on virtual worlds', and in terms of competition, it 'aims for a Web 4.0 that is powered by open and highly distributed technologies and standards that enable interoperability between platforms and networks and freedom of choice for users'.⁸² In our opinion, this statement invites the application of the Digital Markets Act (DMA) to video games and virtual worlds. The Digital Markets Act is the EU's response to entrenched economic power – 'gatekeeping' – in digital markets and it came into force in 2022. It applies to selected 'core platform services', including social media, messaging apps, and online search, by defining what a gatekeeper is and what it can and cannot do. Designated gatekeepers must, for example, allow messaging app interoperability and the installation of third-party app stores on their ecosystems.

Unfortunately, games, virtual worlds or comparable platform elements of eSports and gaming ecosystems are not included as core platform services in the DMA.⁸³ Moreover, the DMA arguably codifies the problems and the business models of the past, limiting its relevance for the future. This is in part because the regulation of the development of platforms or business models is limited by the filtering system of the DMA (Art. 3 (1) and (2) DMA), triggering its application only once a platform has become entrenched.⁸⁴ It is also because the DMA only addresses a closed

<https://www.create.ac.uk/blog/2023/11/14/gaming-industry-competition-copyright-and-business-models/>.

⁸² EC (2023) 4.

⁸³ We however recognise the opening up of app stores with the DMA as a positive development.

⁸⁴ Fabian Ziermann, 'eSports – regulating aspiring gatekeepers?' (D'Kart, 07.12.2021) <https://www.d-kart.de/blog/2021/12/07/esports-regulating-aspiring-gatekeepers/>.

list of core platform services (Article 2(2)), which can be amended only through a legislative procedure (Article 19). This approach treats the symptoms rather than addressing the core problem of anticompetitive business models. Moreover, platforms are incentivised to form their own closed ecosystems as discussed throughout this paper. The platforms that succeed may become dominant for related products and services,⁸⁵ requiring *ex post* intervention for intra-ecosystem abuses. Direct application of the DMA in video games and virtual worlds would help ensure that virtual world markets remain open, as opposed to the much more difficult task of dealing *ex post* with entrenched positions.

It may therefore be necessary to reconsider the list of core platform services and the benchmarks for a gatekeeper designation under the DMA. In particular, given the discussions regarding the separation or aggregation of digital services under the DMA for purposes of designating a gatekeeper,⁸⁶ it is worth exploring whether it might be possible to apply the DMA not to individual games, but to publishers. In other words, if a single game is insufficient to qualify under the DMA's artificial filtering system, it may be worth treating multiple games (or game studios) as a single service to designate a publisher as a gatekeeper.

VI. Conclusion

While the future of virtual worlds remains uncertain, it is clear that they will evolve from existing ecosystems such as video games, app stores, and hardware platforms. Their ultimate architecture will largely reflect the narratives promoted by strong incumbents. These two factors, in turn, have several important regulatory implications for the future of virtual worlds.

The close relationship between video games and virtual worlds makes the latter unlikely to fail, unless video games themselves were to disappear. Because the development of virtual worlds requires significant capabilities, regulation should guard against market concentration. If one vision dominates prematurely, diversity might be forfeited before alternative narratives even emerge. Companies will inevitably leverage power from existing ecosystems to influence virtual world development in their favor. Meta and Apple, for example, are promoting VR-based access to reinforce their own vision of virtual environments.

⁸⁵ Matthew Ball, 'Esports and the Dangers of Serving at the Pleasure of a King' (matthewball.co, 17.04.2020) <https://www.matthewball.co/all/esportsrisks>; J Remy Green, 'All Your Works Belong to Us: New Frontiers for the Derivative Work Right in Video Games' (2018) 19 NC JL & Tech 393; Fabian Ziermann, 'Kartellrecht' in Petschinka (ed), *eSport-Recht* (2023b, Verlag Österreich) 87-109, 114-120.

⁸⁶ Tono Gil, 'Meta tried to get Facebook, Instagram designated as one DMA service, EU official says' (MLex, 29.09.2023) <https://www.mlex.com/mlex/articles/1973020/meta-tried-to-get-facebook-instagram-designated-as-one-dma-service-eu-official-says>.

However, it is important not to treat virtual worlds as monolithic. Each layer presents unique challenges, such as access to funding, (hardware) infrastructure and intellectual property rights. Moreover, while dominant players impose their narrative of virtual world architecture at the platform and access layers, the experience layer remains more open to new entrants. Yet, these new players' opportunities may be constrained by the prevailing architecture, highlighting the need for regulatory assessments to take into account the interconnectedness of the layers.

Ultimately, regulators face a choice: allow virtual worlds to become narrative-driven architectures shaped by a few powerful companies, or intervene early to help define their architecture. As these environments mature, structural change will be much more difficult to implement.

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